

Renewable energy integration with electric vehicle technology: A review of the existing smart charging approaches

Pranjal Barman^{a,*}, Lachit Dutta^b, Sushanta Bordoloi^c, Anamika Kalita^d,
Pronamika Buragohain^g, Swapna Bharali^e, Brian Azzopardi^{f,h}

^a Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati-Technology Innovation & Development Foundation (IITG-TIDF), Guwahati, India

^b Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Gauhati University, Guwahati, India

^c Dept. of Electronics and Communication Engineering, National Institute of Technology, Mizoram, India

^d Physical Sciences Division, Institute of Advanced Study in Science and Technology, Guwahati, 781035, Assam, India

^e Indian Railways, Maligaon, Assam, India

^f MCAST Energy Research Group, Institute of Engineering and Transport, Malta College of Arts, Science and Technology (MCAST), PLA9032, Paola, Malta

^g E&ICT Academy, Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati, India

^h The Foundation for Innovation and Research (FIR.mt)– Malta, 65 Design Centre Level 2, Tower Road, Birkirkara, BKR 4012, Malta

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Electric vehicle (EV)
Renewable energy (RE)
Smart charging
Sustainable mobility
Utility grid

ABSTRACT

The worsening energy crisis, growing environmental consciousness, and the detrimental consequences of climate change, prompted governments to reduce carbon footprints. One of the approaches involved is adopting green energy technology to charge electric vehicles (EVs). The US Department of Energy estimates that EVs may effectively use 60% of the input energy while driving, twice as much as traditional fossil fuel-based vehicles. Although EVs are tremendously efficient, the amount of greenhouse gas emissions they can reduce relies on the source of electricity needed to power them. To summarize the role of RE as a viable charging alternative, in this study, we analyze four essential elements of EV charging infrastructure, RE-enabled smart charging approaches, utility interest and associated challenges and opportunities. First, the existing RE sources employed for EV charging are discussed with their global adoption, advantages and drawbacks and the leading countries. Second, we presented a thorough investigation of energy storage technologies, charging systems, related power electronics, and smart grid integration to facilitate the adoption of RE in EVs. Third, we discussed in-depth the many industry-implemented smart charging approaches with RE in light of the most recent global trend in EV energy usage. Finally, given the inherent challenges associated with realizing the sustainable transition, we discuss the technological challenges and opportunities related to grid integration, renovation, standardization, maintenance, network security and resource optimization. The authors believe this manuscript will serve as an information cornerstone for all the involved parties and scientific communication to gain a deeper understanding and contribute.

1. Introduction

With the continuous growth and development of the countries in terms of infrastructure, automation, transportation, and technology, an extensive quantity of harmful emissions are disseminated into the environment. In addition to industrial pollutants, vehicle traffic contributes significantly to greenhouse gases released into the atmosphere, which causes climate change and contributes to global warming [1–5]. According to recent estimates, the transport industry alone accounts for 25% of CO₂ emissions in European countries [6,7] and 32% in the USA

[8]. The majority of the energy that is used in the transportation industry is derived from products that are based on fossil fuels. As a result, the government's strategies for deploying resources with low carbon footprints were influenced by the rising concern for environmental safety. Due to this concern, numerous automotive companies are taking measures to produce environmentally friendly EVs to achieve global carbon neutrality, which also led to significant capital investment in EV research and development [9].

Globally, sales of EVs have significantly surged in recent years; in 2021, they doubled from the year before, hitting a significant milestone

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: pranjalele@gmail.com (P. Barman).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113518>

Received 1 November 2022; Received in revised form 14 June 2023; Accepted 28 June 2023

Available online 11 July 2023

1364-0321/© 2023 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

of 6.6 million. This market is dominated by China, which accounts for half of global EV sales, but from 2020, sales growth in Europe also becomes substantial. In addition, 2 million EVs were sold in Europe in the first quarter of 2022, an increase of around 75% from the same period in 2021. Statistics suggest that EVs sold globally will increase nearly tenfold by 2030, reaching about 19 million [10], translating to a global share of more than 7% for all vehicles. According to Fig. 1, there will be a 4% increase in power demand by 2030 due to the rising global trend of EV stocks from 2010 to 2021. Utilizing RE and traditional fuel-based power plants would help mitigate this demand, but electrifying road transport and deploying RE will complicate utility distribution management. As EVs proliferate, wind and solar energy are among the fastest-growing technologies, expected to offer more than 35% of the electricity demand by 2050. The 2050 net-zero prediction offers reliable and cheap energy security, supporting strong socioeconomic growth and ensuring universal access to energy. That approach leads to an economically feasible, cost-effective clean, dynamic, and resilient RE dominated energy economy. In addition, this development incorporates cutting-edge technology like vehicle-to-grid (V2G), which will lower the price of RE and pave the way for low-cost charging opportunities [11]. EVs can serve as independent distributed energy sources for the electrical utility grid. Aside from providing power, they can also assist the grid by providing ancillary services such as peak power reduction, spinning reserves, voltage and frequency management etc. [12].

Notably, over the past few years, the integration of RE sources, such as wind and solar PV, has greatly increased in the electrical grid. However, because they are intermittent, they require policies, programs, and technologies to meet the EV charging demand effectively.

In recent years, the emergence of power electronic converters and fast charging has accelerated the EV charging potential, drastically reducing charging time and charge optimization. The charging behavior of different EVs can significantly strain the utility power grid, which may eventually collapse the grid capacity [14]. However, the grid must be safeguarded by ensuring a minimal impact on the load by utilizing smart charging technologies. Precise charge management can be achieved by strategically exploiting the existing power stations and installing a planned network of RE sources for future charging stations [15,16]. Nevertheless, the continuous rise of EVs and sizeable geographical expansion of urban cities make it difficult for a single aggregator to optimize the scheduling process.

In every country, governments are implementing programmes to transition away from traditional energy sources and towards renewable ones, including hydro, bio, solar, wind, and tidal power. Recognizing the necessity, numerous US-based firms recently committed to completely switching from fossil fuel-based energy sources to renewable energy sources. For instance, Austin Energy, a US-based utility company, has created a charging program called Plug-in Everywhere Network that enables EV users to source 100% energy from renewable sources like wind energy. EVgo, a firm that operates a nationwide fast charging network, announced ambitions to entirely run on wind or solar energy for its EV charging network. Charge Forward, a pilot scheme run by

Pacific Gas Electric and BMW, gives customers lower-cost incentives for modifying their charging schedules by utilizing available renewable energy. These efforts are being undertaken to deal with the additional loads EVs place on the electricity grids. Several solutions have been proposed to mitigate grid-related problems, including diverse time-scales, storage, dispatchable loads, and alternate generating capacity [17]. Since all these strategies are supported by EVs connected to the electrical grid, the widespread adoption of EVs will play a significant role in integrating clean RE into existing power systems [18].

Quite a few works are reported on various aspects of the RE source integration with EV charging technology. More recent works have focused on EV charging schedules from RE and automated pricing methods [19,20]. Similar works included V2G and smart charging for power regulation, grid stability, power quality, and reliability [21–23]. A cost-benefit analysis for the bidirectional functionality of vehicle-to-home (V2H) is presented in recent literature [24]. Although there are several investigations on RE source integration with EV charging technology, a cohesive approach is still missing. Therefore, this article surveys the start-of-the-art in both industry and academia, and it provides basic guidance regarding how the approaches might be applied to achieve sustainable mobility and what can be further improved. The current most recent review articles concerning the technological infrastructure, RE-enabled charging approaches and associated challenges are highlighted with a tabular summary in Table 1. In contrast to the existing works, the main contributions of our review are summarized as follow.

1. A thorough analysis of EV charging with RE, charging infrastructure with enabling technologies and grid integration is presented.
2. It investigates some industry-adopted smart charging approaches, such as network-charging, shift-charging, excess-renewable-charging, on-site renewable charging, and managed-charging, that deals with the EV charging demand with RE generation.
3. It provides an insight of the utility interest in RE and the possible alternatives for EV consumers to capture maximum benefits from RE sources, cost effective charging based on vehicle types etc.
4. Challenges and opportunities for future directions of research are proposed.

The rest of the article is organized as follows. Section-2 provide the details of existing renewable resources for EV integration. Section-3 covers the brief description of technological infrastructure for EV integration with RE. Section-4 explains the global EV energy consumption trend. Then Section-5 elaborates the existing RE enables smart charging approaches. Various opportunities and associated challenges are discussed in Section-6. Finally, Section-7 presents the main conclusions and critical findings distinctive from previous studies.

2. Existing renewable resources for EV integration

Integrating EVs with already-existing RE sources can affect the utility

Fig. 1. Global trend of EV stocks from 2010 to 2021 [13].

Table 1
Comparison of method in literature.

Existing Work	Publication Year	Technological Infrastructure	RE Enabled Smart Charging Approaches	Existing Industrial Implications	Technological Hurdles
[25]	2014	✓			
[26]	2019	✓	✓		
[27]	2020				✓
[28]	2022	✓			✓
[29]	2022	✓			✓
[30]	2022		✓		
[31]	2022	✓			✓
[32]	2022			✓	
[33]	2022	✓		✓	
This Manuscript		✓	✓	✓	✓

grid. In this review, we have only focused on wind and solar energies for viable EV charging methodologies. This manuscript does not consider hydropower as this is not an intermittent type of energy. However, we have succinctly listed the primary RE sources that are readily available and can be used for EV charging, along with their corresponding benefits and downsides in [Table 2](#).

3. Technological infrastructure

Despite the steady progress in EV adoption worldwide, it is challenging to prioritize EVs due to the scarcity of charging infrastructures. More public charging stations should be installed to alleviate this drawback, and awareness among the masses about sustainable mobility should be created. In order to install public charging stations, a thorough plan must be created, along with a geographical survey and location planning. As a result of the widespread use of EVs, numerous beneficial applications have emerged in a variety of fields such as.

1. *Electric power market:* The increasing EV charging loads resulting from the widespread use of EVs would present extreme challenges for the power infrastructure. In contrast, EVs are equipped with battery storage, making them distinct from most traditional loads, and they

have an intrinsic capability to participate in the energy market to provide ancillary services via optimized charging, such as V2G.

2. *Transportation system:* The connection between the power distribution network and the transportation network caused by the rising number of EVs has drawn research, development and distribution interest from both the power engineering and the transportation communities.

3. *Distribution system planning:* The distribution system may suffer from improper planning of EV charging stations, which could result in higher power losses and worsened voltage profiles. One of the biggest challenges is organizing the charging infrastructure optimally for the distribution network to operate securely and steadily.

The electricity demand will exceed the power grid’s present load capability. Adopting solar, wind, biomass, and other RE sources can provide a feasible alternative without affecting the environment [45]. It would be a sustainable step in the right direction for a thriving environment. However, RE’s power generation is inconsistent, making them less favourable for practical usage. In order to address this challenge, replacement energy storage devices or customizable dispatch loads to balance renewable energy can be utilized [46]. Nevertheless, it is not an emerging technology such as the flywheel system, supercapacitor,

Table 2
Various renewable resources with their advantages and drawbacks.

RE Sources	Global Share	Advantages	Drawbacks	Leading Countries
Hydro [34–36]	44.44%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Natural abundance ➤ Higher life-spans ➤ Technological maturity ➤ High power capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Secondary emission during installation ◆ Local inhabitant relocation ◆ Disturb aquatic environment ◆ Increases precipitation ◆ Flood and erosion ◆ Affect in wild-life ◆ Water intensive maintenance 	US Canada China Brazil
Wind [37–39]	25.16%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ High technical maturity ➤ Ease of installation over land and water ➤ Higher power capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Bird fatality ◆ Large land acquisition ◆ Intermittent ◆ Susceptible to storms ◆ Noise pollution ◆ Soil deterioration ◆ Large land acquisition ◆ Intermittent and less efficient ◆ Toxic material disposition ◆ Carbon footprints due to manufacturing, transportation, and installation ◆ High replacement cost ◆ Impact of molten salt ◆ Effect on birds ◆ Expensive installation ◆ Distorts nearby scenario ◆ Water intensive maintenance ◆ Intense energy storage dependency ◆ High initial cost 	US India China Germany
Solar PV [28, 40–43]	24.23%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Easy installation ➤ Technical maturity ➤ Relatively low maintenance ➤ Longer life 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Large land acquisition ◆ Intermittent and less efficient ◆ Toxic material disposition ◆ Carbon footprints due to manufacturing, transportation, and installation ◆ High replacement cost ◆ Impact of molten salt ◆ Effect on birds ◆ Expensive installation ◆ Distorts nearby scenario ◆ Water intensive maintenance ◆ Intense energy storage dependency ◆ High initial cost 	US China Germany Japan
Solar thermal [44]	0.24%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Highly efficient ➤ No intermittency ➤ Very long life ➤ Low maintenance ➤ Stationary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ High replacement cost ◆ Impact of molten salt ◆ Effect on birds ◆ Expensive installation ◆ Distorts nearby scenario ◆ Water intensive maintenance ◆ Intense energy storage dependency ◆ High initial cost 	Spain US China South Africa

concentrated solar energy, etc., that has gained popularity in recent years.

Recently, developments in smart technologies, including smart grids, smart metering, wireless sensors, communication frameworks, and power converters, have attracted widespread attention. The opportunities for intelligent charging that use RE will advance more quickly due to these inventions. A typical EV charging ecosystem with several grid-connected RE sources is illustrated in Fig. 2. The various charging infrastructures, including residential and commercial charging outlets, are connected to the distribution utilities. Transmission and distribution control centres act as communication hubs between the grid and the utilities that distribute electricity.

Energy as a value can be retrieved from the fact that a private car is inactive for more than 95% of its lifetime. However, if EVs are integrated into the grid via smart charging technology, their batteries can offer ancillary services to the electrical system and can be charged in the most efficient manner. Therefore, EV owners can use the idle period to trade, sell, or use the electricity stored in their batteries to generate additional income. Moreover, smart charging brings several benefits and provides cost-effective opportunities to use various RE resources. The primary requirements for implementing RE-enabled smart charging systems are energy storage, control equipment, grid integration and smart solution.

3.1. Energy storage technologies

One of the limitations of RE sources is that to prevent power loss, the power generated must be used immediately or supplied to the power grid. Therefore, researchers have suggested adopting stationary energy storage and fast charging systems to eliminate this drawback [47–50]. Energy storage avoids the limitation of RE power interruption and improves EV charging stability by supplying adequate energy during emergencies. The most popular energy storage technologies and their classifications based on energy or power are annotated in Table 3.

The cumulative installed capacity of lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries accounts for 76% of all electrochemical energy storage, followed by sodium-sulfur batteries at 13%, lead batteries at 7%, and redox flow batteries at 3%. In contrast to Li-ion batteries, Nickel-metal-hydride (Ni-MH) batteries [52] have some advantages, like excellent performance characteristics and are easily recyclable [53]. Nickel-cadmium (Ni-Cd), sodium nickel chloride (NaNiCl₂), and sodium sulfur (NaS) batteries have recently gained popularity due to their practical benefits.

Another standard storage method is power-type energy storage, such as supercapacitors (SC) or ultracapacitors (UC), which store energy using the capacitor principle, utilizing two parallel plates and an

Table 3
Classification of Energy Storage [51].

Energy Storage Class	Storage Types	Energy and Power based classifications	Features
Physical	➤ Flywheel Energy Storage	Power Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ High Power Density ➤ Long Life Cycle ➤ High Rate of Charging/Discharging
	➤ Pumped Storage		
Chemical	➤ Battery Energy Storage	Energy Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ High Energy Density ➤ Low Life Cycle
Electromagnetic Energy Storage	➤ Supercapacitor	PowerType	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ High Power Density ➤ Long Life Cycle ➤ High Rate of Charging/Discharging
	➤ Magnetic Energy Storage		

insulator to split them. They outlive other technologies since they do not experience chemical changes, and compared to conventional batteries, the UC has an energy density that is 10% greater and a power density that is 10–100 times higher [54]. However, the inherent drawback of UC is that it needs sophisticated electronic control systems due to the rapid current fluctuation during charging and discharging. The UCs function best in power electronic systems when used as a pulse load or power buffer [55–57]. A new electrolyte and nano-structured electrodes may increase UC’s power density while lowering production costs.

In contrast to batteries and UC storage, a flywheel device stores mechanical energy in the form of kinetic energy by quickly spinning a mass. The Flywheel Energy Source (FES) comprises a flywheel rotor, a motor/generator, and power converters. The FES is crucial for RE storage in wind energy-based applications [58].

The battery and UC can be integrated to create hybrid energy sources (HES) to achieve maximum efficiency [59]. Other hybridization methods are also reported in the literature, for instance, connecting the UC and battery in parallel or using a DC-DC converter [60]. Here, a bidirectional dc-dc converter manages the power flow between the source and the load [61]. The Fuel Cell (FC) can also be coupled with a battery to boost the specific power, energy density, and efficiency. In order to reduce power fluctuations caused by the RE output, hybrid energy storage systems, that is, the combination of energy-type and power-type energy storage, are frequently deployed. The energy type

Fig. 2. Technological infrastructure for EV integration with RE sources

storage can adjust for low-frequency power fluctuations caused by RE, while the power type storage can compensate for high-frequency power fluctuations. The constituents and workflow of a centralized, grid-connected RE storage system and the associated power electronic equipment are depicted in Fig. 3.

3.2. Charging systems and their standardization

Most equipment and appliances require the conversion of generated RE from direct current (DC) to alternating current (AC) before it can be utilized. This is also true when using RE to power an EV; consequently, as RE becomes more prevalent in EVs, there will undoubtedly be a rise in the demand for inverters. Another significant drawback of RE is the generation of low output voltage, making it challenging to be used in inverter-level high-voltage applications. Therefore power converters are essential to boost the voltage level and supply dc power to charge the EV battery at a decent speed via an isolated power converter positioned outside the vehicle. Modern DC based fast chargers require two stages of electronics conversion —rectification with power factor correction (PFC) and a DC/DC conversion to generate regulated dc voltage for convenient charging.

Different existing charging specifications standardized by the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) and International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) levels are depicted in Fig. 4. On-board level 1 or 2 chargers for plug-in electric vehicles (PEVs) provide charging during the day at work or home, while high-power off-board chargers offer fast charging. The benefits of traditional on-board and off-board chargers can be combined to develop an integrated charger to enable fast charging in PEVs [62]. International organizations like SAE and IEC have standardized separate charging levels for diverse vehicle types, charging capacities, and charging behaviours.

3.3. Power electronics

It is essential to remember that the output of all existing RE sources has a built-in stochastic nature. Therefore, different optimization models have been used to improve the grid stability and coordinate with well-planned and variable loads.

A battery charger typically has two phases: an AC-DC converter stage using PFC and a DC-DC stage to regulate the voltages and currents of the batteries. The AC supply is internally rectified to DC for charging EVs in the AC charging arrangement. Faster charging times and longer driving ranges are the two most common client demands, and they directly oppose one another. The charging station has to communicate with the vehicle to inform the available power capacity at the station and how fast it can be delivered with adequate safety. A variety of communication devices has to be integrated to achieve this goal.

Fig. 3. Topological structure of grid-connected RE storage and power electronics system

Fig. 4. Current and voltage comparison of various charging levels [63].

3.4. Grid integration

The utility grid may face difficulties due to the growing number of EVs on the market, which places a heavy burden on the power distribution infrastructure. This requires sufficient network capacity and adequate power supply infrastructure. Maximizing network usage throughout 24 hours may be more cost-effective than upgrading resources to handle peak usage times that happen only occasionally during the day. The emergence of new technologies, such as unidirectional vehicle-to-grid (V1G) and bidirectional V2G technologies, can tackle such a situation by allowing power flow between the EV batteries and the power grid. V1G is the simplest form of smart charging, which allows EVs to adapt the charging rates and time dynamically since the EV and the charging stations are linked with the data connection. The advantage of this technology is that it reduces the charging cost, increases safety, allows vehicle electricity consumption assessment, and makes charging location identification easy.

Unlike V1G, V2G allows a bidirectional power flow between EV and the power grid. However, V2G demands bidirectional charging capability in EVs. The significant advantage of V2G is to balance the grid, specifically when integrated with RE [64]. It offers EV owners a cost-effective service in which they can sell the excess power from their cars at a standard price to the grid. In addition, the on-board batteries of EVs can be used with V2G technology to provide an efficient energy storage system for the utility grid if used appropriately [10]. More innovative and coordinated charging control mechanisms must be

devised in the event of an increase in EV load in order to reduce costs. As RE generation rises, the existing electricity distribution infrastructure must be upgraded to accommodate RE from various sources. The penetration of emerging technologies like vehicle-to-everything (V2X), vehicle-to-building (V2B), V2H, etc. [65], escalates the adoption of RE in a much more effective and efficient way than ever.

3.5. Smart charging

Smart charging refers to an EV charging ecosystem where an EV and a charging device share a standard network alongside a charging operator. In contrast to conventional dumb chargers, smart charging devices are connected to the cloud, allowing the charging station owner to manage, monitor, and restrict the usage of their devices to optimize energy distribution. The flexibility to add and delete features and create a system that meets user requirements is made possible by smart infrastructure. EVs that are smartly charged and connected to the grid work in synergy with the power grid to assist one another. This relationship would not exist without smart charging, and EVs might start to strain the power delivery system and become a burden on the grid. A sophisticated and intelligent back-end system (virtual power plant (VPP)) that powers smart EV charging gives station owners access to real-time monitoring of linked EVs and their charging events [66]. Due to their cloud connectivity, smart stations can be operated depending on various input signals, including variable energy production, local electricity consumption, the number of online EVs, or the use of electrical devices. It aggregates the capacities of heterogeneous distributed energy resources such as solar power equipment, batteries, EVs, wind turbines, etc. This system functions for power generation, intra and inter-electricity trade, sale and purchase power in the market. The structure of a VPP platform for smart charging using standard protocol is shown in Fig. 5.

The VPP establishes a link between the EV, charging station, and the overall charging event. An algorithm will determine the charging tariffs and, based on that real-time price will be charged from the customer, and the mandated amount will be transferred automatically to the station owner. The quintessential characteristic that defines a smart charger are: the stations to be linked to the cloud-based services, the devices should be equipped with a location tracking mechanism employing GPRS or 3G/4G/5G to establish communication with the service providers, the charging devices should be of either Type 2, CHAdeMO or CCS Combo [68].

Various entities must connect within the current stations securely and effectively, a standard protocol that allows such coordination is the Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP) [69]. Regardless of the

manufacturers' features, the OCPP is an open standard that enables the communication between EVs, charging stations, and a central management system (VPP platform in Fig. 5), assuring the management of all the factors involved in the recharging operation. As a direct consequence of this development, electric vehicle (EV) networks are now open and easily accessible, allowing customers to select the network or charging station that best suits their needs. This gives EVs access to operators offering efficient, seamless charging experiences. However, mobile devices, autonomous vehicles, and heterogeneous cyber-physical systems that connect smart automobiles to the smart grid are exposed to cyber-attacks and data security. Despite these challenges, more than 148 nations have extensively used the OCPP, supported by more than 65,000 active EV charging stations [70]. The Open Charge Alliance (OCA), with more than 220 member firms operating in electric mobility, supports the protocol [71]. To ensure the quality of service (QoS) and charge efficiency, OCPP is involved in reserving and controlling the charging procedures [72]. The key benefits of the OCPP over other protocols include its openness and freedom, support for cross-vendor operability, and quick and easy device integration. The demand response protocol OCPP primarily serves as a message exchange between stations and the Charging Station Management System (CSMS). The information is transferred between charging points through LoRaWAN (Long Range WAN) communication protocol. In some urban non-LoS (Line of Sight) circumstances, LoRa modulation, ensures long-range communication. IP (Internet Protocol) is used to implement long-distance communication [67].

The OCPP protocol allows the standardization of communication between a station and a centralized CSMS, as seen in Fig. 5. The sequence of the operations handled by an OCPP to provide quality services during charging is illustrated in Fig. 6. Here, the CSMS, Distribution System Operator (DSO), and the standard protocols of component-to-component communications are presented schematically. CSMS is connected to several charging stations via a local proxy, local controller, and local controller for non-OCPP charging stations. The third-party DSO sends smart charging signals to CSMS based on grid limits. The local controller is optional for controlling one or several charging stations. *Local Proxy* is an optional unit that serves as a router that routes messages to and from multiple stations, especially during the difficulty in network access. Several information exchanges occur throughout each interaction between the CSMS and the charging station. The CSMS can maintain URL addresses for firmware download and updates and manage information about user identification. In addition, it maintains the clock time for synchronizing nodes, metre values indicating the consumption perceived by a user, and status values. In each of the communication nodes, there are unavoidable inherent delays

Fig. 5. VPP platform for smart charging using standard protocol [66,67].

Fig. 6. Services handled by OCPP framework in EV charging [69].

associated. Upgrading the hardware and OCPP version could reduce these communication delays from the network.

Nevertheless, most of these messages are based on web technology and unreliable protocols like HTTP and FTP, which lack standard security measures. When a user participates in the charging process via a smart device, the user action and user device vulnerabilities may indirectly affect the OCPP operations and security. Nevertheless, the latest OCPP offers the features like secure firmware updating, logging and event notification, secure authentication, etc.

3.5.1. Security concerns

Recently, there has been a lot of interest in designing safe charging infrastructure from the scientific and business community. This new system, associated with mobile devices, autonomous vehicles, and heterogeneous cyber-physical systems, is not out of risk and vulnerabilities. The primary security criteria for the OCPP-based EV charging service are availability, integrity, authenticity, and confidentiality. As a result, the mandatory security protocols outlined above apply to all data and information from the EV, including the driver's identity, the State of Charge (SOC), the supply microgrid, billing services, etc. [73]. The main security concerns are the logging and monitoring of the smart charging service, the firmware update procedure, and the compatibility of the various charging types. The entire network must be protected from various OCPP-related attacks, such as physical and cyber-physical ones. In order to address these issues, Multimodal and Multipass Authentication using Contract Certificate (MMA-CC) scheme, and the Message Authentication Code (MAC) methodologies have been used to secure the controller area network [69].

4. Energy consumption trend of EV charging

The annual energy consumption of a BEV or PHEV ranges from 500 kWh to 4350 kWh. In contrast to those vehicles, heavy-duty vehicles like electric buses and trucks require roughly 0.56 to 3.34 kWh per mile. According to the data provided by the U.S. National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), consumption will increase to around 300 TWh by 2030 [74,75]. Fig. 7 shows the estimated energy demand in 2025 and 2030 for E.V. types in various leading countries. Utilities that provide electricity and clean energy have started initiatives that allow E.V. smart charging with RE sources in response to the anticipated rise in E.V. demand. Some states of the USA already have demand-based RE procurement to match their overall electricity requirement. Existing initiatives include green tariffs, solar community projects, direct power purchase agreements with renewable energy sources, green pricing

Fig. 7. Estimated energy consumption in Light Duty Vehicle (LDV) and Heavy Duty Vehicle (HDV) for the years 2025 and 2030 [13].

initiatives, and services based on RE certificates [76–83]. However, the programs above do not take into account EV loads. These schemes have not accelerated all of the advantages that utilities and customers might gain by tightly tying the duration of EV charging to renewable energy generation. The utility industries and other third parties have developed a variety of smart charging strategies for RE-based EV charging, which will be covered in detail in the section that follows. The approaches for creating such an approach include granting access to RE, encouraging charging during off-peak hours, time-based fee structures, etc.

5. Renewable energy enabled smart charging approaches

Utilities are responding to this anticipated demand for EVs, electricity, and green energy with new pricing and initiatives to facilitate charging using RE sources. In the United States, utility and third-party offerings have long allowed customers to purchase RE annually to meet their overall electricity demands. Examples include green pricing programs or green tariffs that allow large customers to purchase substantial green energy at a special rate. Later on, community solar programs and direct power purchase agreements with RE sources are introduced. These offerings, however, have not been formulated for EV charging.

Consequently, the variable EV loads depending on vehicle type and charging patterns failed to capture all the grid benefits offered by RE. The grid benefits that EV charging programmes can offer have been

more efficiently tapped into by new utility programmes, most geared towards light-duty vehicles. Despite different charging patterns for different EVs, their use, and customer needs, some EV charging demand can be flexible to align with grid requirements or RE availability. In this section, we have explored five existing smart charging approaches, their utility programs, and the strategies adopted by third parties to enable customers to match EV charging demand with RE generation.

5.1. Network charging

Network charging is a practical smart charging approach that enables EV owners to charge their vehicles using RE. Despite many charging stations, only a small fraction of these facilities allow customers to use their electricity exclusively from RE [75]. The network charging program usually allows the customers to subscribe to a fixed amount of EV charging that is guaranteed to be matched with RE. These programs can also be designed to encourage the customers to charge the EVs at times that are beneficial for the grid or align with renewable energy production. Customers typically can avail network charging of EVs under a variety of pricing structures, including pay-as-you-go plans, fixed-price monthly subscriptions, free network access with government subsidies, and workplace contracts for employees. To participate, customers must register through a utility program or an EV charging network provider. Membership plans are made available with fixed monthly fees for the customers. Customers are also being encouraged to avail off-peak charging at their residences on weekends or at night through network charging. The wind energy generated by wind-based RE resources is more potent at night. Therefore, integrating the grid with wind-based RE will significantly lessen the grid stress at night. The Plug-in Everywhere Network, a network charging service created by Austin Energy, enables users to procure all their charging electricity demand from wind energy.

5.1.1. Methodology

The network charging technique aims to lower carbon emissions while advancing essential technologies like demand response and energy storage. A schematic diagram showing the various components of network charging methodologies is illustrated in Fig. 8. The key goals were to prevent charging during peak hours, synchronize EV charging with RE generation, and boost customer satisfaction while maintaining cheap rates and promoting customer choice. Utilities have access to several techniques to achieve the goals, such as incentives, behavioral changes, and curtailment programmes using automated thermostats or built-in EV telematics. However, rates, which generate distinct pricing signals that consumers can react to, are likely the most effective way to influence charging behavior. The introduction of the Time-of-use (ToU) rate can track daytime electricity use. The utilities are therefore designed to avoid the complexity and administrative overhead of delivering real-time rates while yet more closely aligning user behavior with the utility’s actual expenses. In the USA, more than 25 utilities offer such rates to encourage EV owners nationwide.

5.1.2. Pilot project by utility industry

A pilot programme called Plug-In Everywhere from Austin Energy, a US-based company, combines unlimited charging at designated stations and unlimited off-peak charging at residences as part of a membership. They established off-peak charge times throughout the day on weekends and 7:00 p.m. to 2:00 p.m. on working days. For off-peak residential charging, customers can choose flat rate fees of \$30/month for a requirement of beneath 10 kW and \$50/month for a requirement exceeding 10 kW [84]. The monthly membership cost is levied with an on-peak adder top-up if the EV is charged during on-peak hours. The top-up is fixed at \$0.40/kWh and \$0.14/kWh during summer and winter, respectively. A sub-meter linked to a 455 level-2 (240 V) charging point installed at the client’s residence measures the energy used for EV charging. Participation requires several eligibility criteria;

Fig. 8. Network charging methodology

for instance, they must have an EV, a separate residence and an electric meter, and a subscription with the utility industry.

5.1.3. Rate design and promotion

Based on the anticipated demand for EVs, the rate has been determined through consultation with several host company subsidiaries. To keep the cost reasonable, the rates team estimated the energy consumption of typical EVs and Level-2 home chargers and suggested two charging tiers: one for chargers under 10 kW and another for chargers exceeding 10 kW. According to the estimate, EV owners in the US would spend an average of \$26 for a standard residential rate. Once the tariff had been created, it needed to be approved by business leaders, the Electric Utility Commission, and the City Council. The billing services are then responsible for installing and configuring the meter in the customer’s residence to accomplish scheduling and billing operations. A pilot team is established during the promotional phase, and they employ a thorough marketing strategy to inform EV owners and electrical contractors of the program’s components and installation needs. The primary platforms for notifying beneficiaries about programme developments, enrollment incentives, etc., are e-mail, text, and web

services. Utility industries may employ data-driven segmentation to locate and target EV owners likely to respond to advertising. To provide personalized and targeted marketing communications, the marketing division works in conjunction with the data analytics and business intelligence division. Finally, it collects customer feedback to improve their product and services.

5.2. Shift charging

Shift charging is another smart approach that aims to match the timing of RE generation with EV charging. Shift charging utility programs encourage EV charging at times, which is more convenient to the grid during off-peak periods or when RE generation is high. The utilities offer the customers discounted rates during these preferential times, which can offset any potential premium for RE. The savings of using excess wind generation allow the utility to offer 100% renewable charging without additional charges to the customers [75]. The shift charging approach mutually benefits the utility and its customers. The utility saves the expense associated with system management, and the customers are free of paying a premium. Some other programs are designed to link EV customers' time-of-use (ToU) rates with RE options [85]. The ToU rates allow utility customers to pay different prices for their electricity, depending on their time of consumption. Typically, higher tariffs are imposed during peak hours when there is a strong demand for electricity from the grid, and lower rates are charged during off-peak hours [86,87]. This approach prompts EV owners to voluntarily shift their loads away from peak demand hours, helping to avoid grid stress. However, once the availability of renewable sources reaches sufficient levels on the system, the preferred grid times could be modified to when excess renewable are available.

The customers can sign up separately for an EV-ToU rate and green pricing program. Although ToU rates are not novel, utilities are increasingly making them available to EV owners. It offers them either

as a residential rate where all household energy is measured on a single meter or as a separately metered rate specific to EV charging. In some cases, utilities offer EV-ToU rates alongside a green pricing program or offer EV customers the option to charge their EVs with RE. Unlike the network charging approach adopted by Austin Energy, it does not include a charging network. There is another approach in which customers interested in participating in a ToU rate confirming RE for other applications may choose to charge their EV. An existing utility like Great River Energy offers special rates for customers willing to charge at night when the wind is abundant, and the load on the grid is less [88].

5.2.1. Rate design for shift charging

The shift charging utility industries offer special coupons for customers willing to charge their EVs at night when the wind is abundant in the locality. For instance, the US-based Great River Energy launched a program named Revolt which is the first program of its kind to offer a RE alternative free of charge. Customers can separately participate in an EV-ToU rate as a part of the green pricing program. Therefore, the customer provides grid benefits by charging at preferred grid times, however, it does not necessarily ensure that the EVs are charging exclusively from RE source. The utilities offer the customers a residential rate where all household energy is measured on a single meter or as a separately metered rate specific to EV charging. In the ToU rate with RE option, customers can participate in a ToU rate and add renewable energy sign up for the ToU rate first and then choose to add renewable energy charging. This approach differs from the conventional green pricing examples offered by Great River Energy. Various utilities offering shift charging incentives with their respective charging methods are presented in Table 4.

5.3. Charging with excess renewable

In this program, smart charging is aligned with the excess energy

Table 4
Charging approaches with RE sources.

Charging approaches	Utility industry	Types of RE	Charging methods and types	Incentives&offers
Network charging	Austin Energy [89]	Wind	Home charging: Level-2 Community charging: Level-2(120 V/240 V)	50% on purchase and installation cost of Level-2 chargers \$1500 for DC fast charging, \$4000 for Level-2 and \$700 for Level-1 rebate depend on model demand, site and compatibility.
	EV Go: Fast Charging [90]	Solar and wind	DC Fast charging and Level-2 charging	Purchase of an all-electric or PEV will receive a federal tax credit of upto \$7,500
Shift charging	Great River Energy [91]	Wind	Park charging	Charging of 5000kWh annually per customer for 10 years. 15% of EV's total cost. Incentives on excess renewable energy use.
	Sacramento Municipal Utility District (SMUD) [92]	Solar	Home and public charging, Level-1and Level-2 charging	Incentive on off peak 0.015/kWh credit per day charging
	Xcel Energy [93]	Wind and solar	Home charging, Level-2 Residential charging Level-2	Off peak incentives
Charging with access renewable	Potomac Electric Power Company (PEPCO) [94]	Solar, biomass wind, and other	Home charging	Premium relieved during off peak charging
	Southern California Edison [95]	Not yet adopted	Home charging, level-1, level-2, DC fast charging	Weekday off peak rebate. IntroduceToU rate to match the time of customer
On-site renewable	Hawaiian Electric Company (HECO) [96]	Solar, wind, hydro, Bio-mass and Geothermal	DC fast charging	Cash incentive for additional battery. ToU incentive for overnight energy used. Intensives of \$0.33/kWh and \$0.50/kWh during excess renewable on the grid
	Google	Solar and wind	Workplace charging	-
	Direct TV	Solar	Workplace charging	-
	San Diego's Solar-to-EV Pilot Project (California)	Solar	Resident charging	Off peak incentive
	Tesla and LomboXnet's Smart Solar Charging Project	Solar	Public charging	-
Managed Charging	Tennessee Valley Authority and Electric Power Board Solar Charging Stations [97]	Solar	Public charging	-
	SMUD [92]	Solar	Level-1 and Level-2 charging	\$150 to \$170 one time and quarterly combined

generated by the RE sources to help grid integration. Here, the electricity unit rates vary inversely in accordance with the generation of RE to drive the loads to periods when the system produces more RE than it needs [98]. Utilities utilize ToU rates to address RE, especially in areas where RE sources are widely used [99]. ToU rates can assist in addressing some of the issues related to the daily and seasonal patterns of RE generation by enhancing overall system flexibility and moving load demand [75]. Currently, only a few places, like Hawaii and California, where there may be an excess of solar output during the noon, have these problems [100]. However, as solar and wind power capacity is expected to grow substantially over the next five years, more utilities may be interested in linking EV demand and renewable supplies. Utilities like Southern California Edison established a time-based rate that encourages customers to charge on weekdays and during off-peak hours on weekends when solar is abundant during the day, and wind is in excess during the night. It does not directly provide RE for an EV load but instead tries to match the EV charging time with excess solar generation on the grid.

5.3.1. Rate design for excess renewable

Utilities are utilizing ToU rates to address renewable energy in areas with a high penetration of renewable sources, and curtailment is required. For example, solar generation is high at midday in summer and wind generation at night in winter and spring. The ToU-D-PRIME rate introduced by Southern California Edison is a part of the excess renewable smart charging approach. It encourages customers to charge on weekdays and weekends during off-peak hours when solar power is abundant (8 a.m.–4 p.m.) and then again at night (9 p.m.–8 a.m.) when wind power can be abundant. The Hawaiian Electric Company introduced a ToU rate for EV charging, known as Schedule-ToU-EV, that gave customers a lower price for overnight energy usage. Although the ToU rates fluctuate by location and are subject to monthly adjustments, costs are lowest during the midday period, when solar and other renewable energy is most abundant and at an excess on the grid. Some relevant examples of charging with RE sources are presented in Table 4.

5.4. On-site renewables

In the on-site renewable approach, EV charging is paired with on-site RE generation, typically solar PV, for residential or commercial applications. When EV charging is paired with on-site RE, several approaches can be used, such as co-locating the systems to avoid the effect of charging times, managed charging to control load or integrating battery storage [101–103]. During the daytime, the solar canopy charges the EVs directly connected with solar power and stores any excess RE in connected batteries [75]. The stored energy can either be used to continue charging EVs at the time when solar energy is not available. It can also export energy to the grid during night times. The on-site renewable approaches have advantages, like being relatively easy to manage for residential customers. However, it could be challenging to manage the instantaneous load when several EVs charge at once. Google, DirecTV, Tesla, etc., industries have rolled out several programs coupled with solar and batteries to enable on-site RE charging.

5.5. Managed charging

To more closely connect EV charging to RE, another smart charging strategy is to create programs that regulate the timing of EV charging, either at residence or workplace [104]. Managed charging is another name for controlled charging [105]. This can be categorized as unidirectional managed charging (V1G) or bidirectional managed charging (V2G). The V1G charging system regulates and optimizes charging time, rate, and duration by adjusting to pricing signals and power system requirements. The utility operator sends necessary signals that carry information on the present status of the grid and the RE availability. In the V2G, as opposed to the V1G, an EV serves as an energy storage that is

distributed in nature and capable of supplying extra power to the grid as needed [75,106,107]. Using this method, utilities can remotely manage EV charging by altering the charging pace in response to grid demand. Unidirectional charging from the electrical grid to the EV is referred to as V1G. Nevertheless, managed charging requires an additional communication system among the EV, charge point, and utility. These communication systems may be either wireless, cellular, or some other telecommunication. In this operation, Level-1 and Level-2 chargers are preferred for load management that can handle the disruption from the utility.

Level-1 charging uses a standard wall outlet with a 120 V rating, charging an EV up to 5 miles/hour. Similarly, Level-2 chargers are rated from 220 V to 240 V, charging up to 25 miles/hour and are readily available in residential or workplace charging systems. DC fast charging is another alternative that has gained popularity in recent years. It is the fastest way to charge EVs that can charge up to 80% capacity in less than 30 min. Despite having fast charging capability, the DC fast charging is less suitable than other levels in load management in managed charging. The managed charging can also be automated so that the customers can acquire the benefits without managing the time manually. Variable RE can be dealt with and made more accessible to clients using V2G. When RE generation is low, the EV batteries recharged with it can discharge the electricity back onto the grid [108].

Additionally, through controlled charging schemes, consumers, utilities, and even car manufacturers can regulate the timing of EV charging to coincide with the availability of clean energy sources and grid requirements. The managed charging ecosystem of RE is depicted in Fig. 9; it comprises electricity generation/distribution, communication control, smart inverters, a weather forecasting station, an e-mobility service provider (e-MSP) and ToU-based offerings and tariffs.

The weather forecasting system collects quantitative information on the status of the atmosphere, land, and oceans and utilizes meteorology to predict how the atmosphere will change at a specific site. As a result, it produces the estimated market parameters for the possible variation in solar and wind energy. Through e-MSP, the created market signal has been transmitted to the electricity substation, charging stations, and EV owners. The price of the tariffs fluctuates in real-time in accordance with the demand-supply curve, so owners are encouraged to charge their vehicles when the cost is lower.

5.6. Industrial implications

The current utility programs focus on light-duty vehicles to efficiently capture the grid benefits. Several new programs are designed to link EV charging during the midday to maximize solar energy. Likewise, the EVs are linked when the excess wind generation is primarily available at night. Nevertheless, the charging pattern is not consistent with all types of EVs. It varied depending on the types, utilization as well as customer requirements. Until now, some EV charging demands can be flexible to align with renewable energy availability. For example, residential customers and some vehicle fleets may be able to shift charging to preferred times, mainly if they receive financial incentives. Several utility industries and third parties have used to enable customers to match EV charging demand with RE generation. Austin Energy and EVgo introduced a network charging model through which customers pay for every use or a monthly flat rate to use public chargers and charge with RE. Industries like Great River Energy and Xcel Energy encourage EV owners to shift their charging time during off-peak periods or when RE generation is high. Hawaiian Electric Company introduced ToU rates that match EV charging with the timing of excess renewables. The companies like Google, DirecTV or Tesla couple the EV charging with RE from on-site solar panels. San Diego Gas & Electric and BMW adopted managed charging programs that can align EV charging with RE output or grid requirements. The industrial implications of various smart charging approaches, along with their charging method, types, incentives and offers, are presented in Table 4.

Fig. 9. Managed charging ecosystem with RE.

Due to the necessity of the vehicles for meeting service requirements, there may be restrictions on the ability to change charging times for other vehicle types, including buses and medium-to heavy-duty vehicles. Utility programs that address these shifts in demand can help customers meet their clean energy goals and benefit utilities in the transition to a low-carbon grid as vehicle electrification and renewable source deployment grow in the coming years. Optimization criteria are essential for all types of charging, and consumers can employ flexibility options to control their usage and synchronize it with the generation of rooftop solar panels to reduce the electricity charge. Furthermore, they can support the wholesale power market and balance price volatility and grid stability. One way to get smart charging is to ensure that the market and regulations show the importance of system flexibility.

Moreover, the value of the distribution system improves with the smooth variation of the charging price index over time. Table 5 enlists the few nations with each component needed to implement smart charging. This assessment is based on a few parameters, such as introducing ToU tariff, ancillary services, service provider’s flexibility in the open market and formulation of policies and standards. Although several other countries are transitioning towards RE and adopting RE-enabled smart charging approaches, they are yet in the early stage and might require further infrastructure and planning to host the smart charging option.

6. Opportunities and challenges

The mobility industry has been transforming towards a new technological shift with the commitment to being less polluting, sustainable, and highly efficient in the long run. The future of transportation will remain in a state of being environmentally friendly, safer at all levels, and capable of communicating with other systems. With the advanced

Table 5 Countries that have sufficient infrastructure and planning to establish smartcharging technology [10].

Country	TOU tariff peaks/off-peak night/day	Ancillary Services	Service provider’s flexibility in energy market	Smart Charging policies and standard
Australia	Introduced	Established	Established	Yet to be introduced
China	Established	”	”	In progress
France	”	”	”	Introduced
Germany	”	”	”	Established
Greece	”	”	”	”
India	Introduced	”	”	In progress
USA	Established	”	”	Established
Japan	”	”	”	In progress
UK	”	”	”	Established
Italy	”	”	”	”

modules of high-capacity energy storage systems for hybrid and pure electric vehicles, renewable resources, biofuels, and innovative light-weight materials, we have witnessed the emergence of technologies we never believed in ten years ago.

As RE sources continuously penetrate major urban areas, EV charging stations can be built using renewable resources to facilitate the existing utility grid. These distributed energy sources will also cut the additional investment to upgrade the available grids. However, the grid might face certain constraints when the congestion of charging EVs is very high. The car owners will evaluate the new environment considering the charging time, user safety, reliability, quality, and price. The EV load coordination essentially has so many challenges, which impinges local instability in voltage levels, re-routing the power to minimize the circuit distance, enhancing the upstream transformer capacity, connecting automatic voltage control transformers, upgrading the thermal capacity of the grid, reactive power compensation, modifications to the grid architecture, etc. Although several applications have demonstrated the potential of RE integration with the grid, additional research is necessary to comprehend the advantages and drawbacks of the subject matter exhaustively. Here are some crucial concerns that, in our opinion, among many others, call for additional study in this area.

6.1. Grid integration

According to the Global EV Outlook 2020, the anticipated unmanaged peak load will be less than 10% in 2030. The significant challenge faced by the cities where EV growth with RE is high is upgrading the existing infrastructure. The challenge is often to make loads more flexible. The opportunities are for the participation of EVs in local or bulk flexibility through V1G or V2G to help increase RE uptake. After 2030, significant upgrades are needed relying on the effective demand-response measures related to EV charging. Further, technical innovation is on the offing due to the research conducted by numerous industry and academic institutions to develop novel grid integration frameworks to assist the widespread adoption of EVs.

6.2. Renovation of existing infrastructures

The existing infrastructures, like residential buildings, community parking, commercial buildings, etc., need major renovation to build a healthy EV charging ecosystem. The possibility of incorporating RE (solar panels) into the existing infrastructures will lessen the strain on the grid and reduce constant dependency on it. It will help mitigate the burden of frequent visits to nearby charging stations. Additionally, the surplus electricity generated by the RE source can be exported to the grid using a grid-tie-inverter.

6.3. Grid renovation for highway charging

Existing grids are adequate to accommodate available EVs in urban and rural areas until 2030. However, highway charging has some inherent challenges, especially in remote areas. In such cases, grid renovation will be a significant expense. Adoption of fast charging could alleviate some of these challenges. Alternative solutions, such as installing battery storage or distributed RE integration, can reduce renovation costs.

6.4. Lack of distribution grid transparency

The challenges to forecasting real-time load data are not yet robust from medium and low voltage systems. Adopting smart meters and grid sensing equipment can help to accurately aggregate data and help seamlessly analyze the real-time load information. Along with the incorporation of smart equipment, an online framework that connects the EVs, charging stations, RE sources, and the power grid is indispensable for continuous monitoring of the overall status of the power distribution system. With each RE source having its energy conversion system, associated components, and capabilities, ensuring the interoperable and uninterrupted power transfer between utility and grid becomes intimidating. To mitigate this burden, a universal framework to standardize energy conversion technologies is essential; in doing so, the RE sources should be treated both as standalone and as a part of the smart grid.

6.5. Inadequate market framework

The regulatory framework of most countries does not provide a mechanism for contracting flexibility services among power distributors, system operators, and consumers. The synergy between the transmission distribution needs to be strengthened to ensure flexibility, congestion-free, and system-balancing services. A new structure must be established for individual customers to achieve the minimum market entry requirement. Furthermore, small consumers lack the necessary knowledge of the design and operation of the wholesale energy market, and they have no desire to become actively involved with it. It is necessary to unlock the flexibility contained in a number of smaller loads, allowing them to interact as wholesale in the energy market.

6.6. Lack of standardization

In contrast to electric cars, the charging port differs for different manufacturers of two and three-wheelers. This is due to the lack of standardization. The situation is further exacerbated by the presence of many EV developers voluntarily creating their own standards in the segments mentioned above. Consequently, EV users face difficulty charging their vehicles at different manufacturers' charging stations. The unavailability of a benchmark thus threatens the large-scale adoption of EVs in this segment. Therefore, the authorities must impose a unified standard framework for the two- and three-wheeler EV segment to increase its adaptability.

6.7. Maintenance

The sophistication and complexity of hardware-software co-design have drastically increased in smart grid systems due to the integration of several sources of RE. Moreover, with the advancement of technology, the smart grid framework is subjected to periodic modifications such as resource linkage, instantaneous failures, equipment and service upgradation, etc. Maintaining and modifying the smart grid framework affect the runtime services and disrupt the entire network. In order to tackle the failure due to system maintenance and providing uninterrupted services requires, highly skilled engineers for necessary grid maintenance. System maintenance tasks must be executed to tackle such issues

by routing the service providers to another network. Skilled labours are indispensable for necessary grid maintenance, routing, and upgradation.

6.8. Biodiversity

The extraction of RE degrades biodiversity, such as soil deterioration, toxic material disposition, bird fatality, noise, changing nearby temperature, carbon monoxide emission, unpleasant smell, etc. This is an inherent drawback of RE generation. In addition, the transportation and installation of the RE generation infrastructure are associated with a significant carbon footprint. The generation of RE without affecting the ecosystem is still a technological challenge in specific geographical locations.

6.9. Electronic waste management

Electronic waste management involves using safe practices to recover and recycle the electronic components used in RE generating and distribution systems. It also involves developing the appropriate tools and methods to manage and degrade the e-waste. This is done to lessen the harmful effect on the environment due to e-waste. The existing e-waste management processes are expensive and still in their nascent stage. Therefore, there is enough headroom for research in this direction.

6.10. Dependence on rare earth metals

Although RE resources generate electricity, storage of the generated energy requires batteries. The batteries require sixfold more minerals than ICEVs. Undoubtedly, the earth's crust contains a plentiful supply of the raw ingredients needed to manufacture batteries. Nevertheless, the technology present currently is unable to extract them efficiently. So, extracting those following sustainable guidelines to meet the ever-increasing demand will be of great concern in the near future. The lack of high-quality materials may prompt battery manufacturers to use low-grade minerals, degrading the battery's performance. Extracting massive quantities of raw materials without affecting the environment remains a technological challenge.

6.11. Network security

Smart charging is a two-way transmission protocol between the EV and the charging station to exchange information. Anxiety regarding the security of the communication network in smart charging exists as it faces a threat from malicious activists and hackers. Data security is a serious concern; personal data, EV data, data and identity of charging stations, cashless transactions, and banking details must all be protected during V2G communication. In order to ensure privacy, legal frameworks should be formulated explicitly for smart charging infrastructures. The framework must define how private data should be collected, protected, stored and disclosed.

6.12. Availability

The stochastic nature of the RE makes the EV owner's access to the chargers limited at some particular time. Despite the adoption of fast and smart charging by the charging stations, it is undeniable that RE-based charging access is limited. This issue could be more serious when EV deployment rises over time and the power grid fails to deliver the required load. To address this issue, government policymakers must join hands with private sectors and researchers to adopt strategies for proper location planning, infrastructure development, and installation of more RE sources.

6.13. Virtualization security

Security in the core EV charging ecosystem, several renewable sources coexist, sharing the same network in a centralized manner. Therefore fault in one framework may result in the collapse of the entire network. Therefore adequate network management has to be involved in dealing with such congestion. For instance, cutting-edge technologies like cloud computing, blockchain, AI, and ML may be used with smart charging technologies to create a robust infrastructure for the EV sector.

6.14. Resource optimization

Resource optimization is a challenging issue in the RE integration with the EV. Resource optimization deals with allocating and managing network resources in the most efficient way possible. It involves multiple domains, such as IT industries, digital agencies, service operators, etc. It also requires high-end software and human resources, increasing the service cost.

7. Conclusion

Though the shifting of energy sources in vehicular technologies from fossil fuel to varied RE is nascent, a common goal is to promote green energy and provide sustainable mobility. In a short span, more and more vehicle manufacturers have pushed themselves from the ICEV to EV because of sustainable policies adopted by governments worldwide and consumer awareness. Moreover, efficient energy usage, autonomous driving, eco-routing navigation, noise and vibration-free, etc., are the exciting features of EVs that make them vehicles of the future. Smart charging balances the supply and demand of electricity from the utility grid since it provides enough power resources for generation or storage and a sizable network capacity. In smart charging, an EV charging system uses a variety of protocols and standards to control network connection since it requires multiple entities to communicate safely and effectively. Interoperability enables aggregators to attract EVs effectively along with their residence charging facilities. The minimum requirements for chargers must be highly flexible to accommodate both public and private use, and the standards should be comprehensive enough to address data accessibility and cyber security.

It is acknowledged that with the ever-increasing demand for EVs, more charging stations are needed to fulfill the energy need, making integration of RE sources indispensable to achieve sustainable objectives. However, for EVs to reach their full potential as green transportation, integrating smart EV charging with renewable energy sources is inevitable. In this field, several innovations have enabled citizens to realize sustainable green EV charging technology to minimize the operating cost of charging during day time abundant solar irradiation or surplus wind energy during the night. This smart charging approach is achieved by juxtaposing an intelligent algorithm to automatically vary the tariff rates in real time for charging during peak and off-peak hours, which results in cost-effective and efficient energy consumption.

To achieve sustainable mobility, government policymakers must provide financial aid, offer subsidies and research grants, create job opportunities and feed-in-tariff etc. Emphasis should also be placed on educating the general public about the advantages of adopting RE, both economically and environmentally, by funding and disseminating research findings, carrying out demonstration projects, and using a range of news and media, pamphlets, and the internet. Additionally, some methodologies, such as activity-based or agent-based models, encourage the adoption of EV charging at the home level by enhancing grid transparency and streamlining transportation planning through capacity maps. This requires the need for cooperation to solve common problems among the generation, transmission and distribution industries. To reap the benefits of scale and aggregation, policymakers must balance imposing norms and enabling the market to innovate without further restrictions. The traditional unregulated charging of EVs

eliminates their ability to be used as a distributed energy source. Policymakers can set the minimum standards based on market demand, both for EV uptake and the state of the power system.

Furthermore, the opportunities and challenges that may appear before long are discussed elaborately with possible solutions. Despite the existence of numerous RE sources, the current EV charging technology exclusively adopts solar, wind, and hydropower. Future research must examine the potential for utilizing other variable RE sources, such as geothermal, oceanic, or tidal energy. Geolocation-specific RE sources can also be explored; for instance, integrating tidal energy with the wind in coastal regions may be more advantageous for EV charging. Similarly, charging with geothermal energy in a location with high energy concentration can be another scope. Moreover, as the technology evolves new unforeseen challenges and opportunities will come that will require new scientific breakthroughs in the RE space.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgement

This work is supported in part by the European Commission H2020 TWINNING Networking for Excellence in Electric Mobility Operations (NEEMO) Project under Grant 857484. Authors would also like to acknowledge the support in part by the European Commission H2020 TWINNING JUMP2Excel (Joint Universal activities for Mediterranean PV integration Excellence) project under grant no. 810809, the TRANSIT (TRANSITion to sustainable future through training and education) project funded by the European Union, grant agreement no. 101075747 and PROMISE (Photovoltaics Reliability Operations and Maintenance Innovative Solutions for Energy Alliance), grant agreement no. 101079469.

References

- [1] Ma T, Osama A-M. Optimal charging of plug-in electric vehicles for 890 a car-park infrastructure. *IEEE Trans Ind Appl* 2014;50.4:2323–30.
- [2] Saber A-Y, Venayagamoorthy GK. Plug-in vehicles and renewable energy sources for cost and emission reductions. *IEEE Trans Ind Electron* 2011;58.4:1229–38.
- [3] Yildirim M, Catalbas M-C, Gulden A, Kurum H. Computation of the speed of four in-wheel motors of an electric vehicle using a radial basis neural network. *Engg., Techn. Appl. Sci. Research* 2016;6.6:1288–93.
- [4] Lee C-H-T, Chau K-T, Liu C. Design and analysis of an electronic geared magnetless machine for electric vehicles. *IEEE Trans Ind Electron* 2016;63.11:6705–14.
- [5] Emadi A, Lee Y-J, Rajashekara K. Power electronics and motor drive in electric, hybrid electric, and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles. *IEEE Trans Ind Electron* 2008;55.6:2237–45.
- [6] Towards a resource-efficient transport system. 2010. Copenhagen, Denmark.
- [7] Martin H, Buffat R, Bucher D, Hamper J, Raubal M. Using rooftop photovoltaic generation to cover individual electric vehicle demand-A detailed case study. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2022;157:111969.
- [8] Inventory of U.S.. Greenhouse gas emissions and sinks: 1990–2010. Washington, DC, USA: Tech. Rep; 2012. EPA 430-R-12-001.
- [9] Andrew B. Green technologies and the mobility industry. SAE; 2011.
- [10] Bibra Ekta Meena, et al. Global EV outlook 2022. International Energy Agency; 2022.
- [11] Blumberg G, Broll R, Weber C. The impact of electric vehicles on the future European electricity system—A scenario analysis. *Energy Pol* 2022;161:112751.
- [12] Richardson DB. Electric vehicles and the electric grid: a review of modeling approaches, impacts, and renewable energy integration. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2013;19:247–54.
- [13] Outlook IEA, Global EV. Securing supplies for an electric future. 2022. 2022.
- [14] Gupta V, Konda S-R, Kumar R, Panigrahi B-K. Collaborative multi-aggregator electric vehicle charge scheduling with PV-assisted charging stations under variable solar profiles. *IET Smart Grid* 2020;3.3:287–99.

- [15] Mwasilu F, Justo J-J, Kim E-K, et al. Electric vehicles and smart grid interaction: a review on vehicle to grid and renewable energy sources integration. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2014;34:501–16.
- [16] Jin R, Wang B, Zhang P, et al. Decentralised online charging scheduling for large populations of electric vehicles: a cyber-physical system approach. *Int J Parallel, Emergent Distributed Syst* 2013;28.1:29–45.
- [17] Harvey LDD. *Energy and the new reality 2: carbon-free energy supply*. London: Earthscan; 2010.
- [18] Lund H, Kempton W. Integration of renewable energy into the transport and electricity sectors through V2G. *Energy Pol* 2008;36:3578–87.
- [19] European Commission. *White Paper on transport Roadmap to a single European transport area: towards a competitive and resource-efficient transport system*. 2011. Luxembourg.
- [20] Xiang W, Kunz T, St-Hilaire M. Controlling electric vehicle charging in the smart grid. Seoul, South Korea: IEEE World Forum on Internet of Things (WF-IoT); 2014. p. 341e6.
- [21] Lehtola T, Zahedi A. Electric vehicle to grid for power regulation: a review. In: *IEEE international conference on power system technology (POWERCON)*; 2016. 1e6. Wollongong, NSW.
- [22] Meng J, Mu Y, Jia H, Wu J, Yu X, Qu B. Dynamic frequency response from electric vehicles considering travelling behavior in the Great Britain power system. *Appl Energy* 2016;162:966e79.
- [23] Pirouzi S, Aghaei J, Niknam T, Farahmand H, Korpas M. Exploring prospective benefits of electric vehicles for optimal energy conditioning in distribution networks. *Energy* 2018;157:679e89.
- [24] Colmenar-Santos A, Palacio-Rodriguez C, Rosales-Asensio E, Borge-Diez D. Estimating the benefits of vehicle-to-home in islands: the case of the Canary Islands. *Energy* 2017;134:311e22.
- [25] Ellabban O, Abu-Rub H, Blaabjerg F. Renewable energy resources: current status, future prospects and their enabling technology. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2014; 39:748–64.
- [26] Colmenar-Santos A, Munoz-Gomez AM, Rosales-Asensio E, Lopez-Rey A. Electric vehicle charging strategy to support renewable energy sources in Europe 2050 low-carbon scenario. *Energy* 2019;183:61–74.
- [27] Sinsel SR, Riemke RL, Hoffmann VH. Challenges and solution technologies for the integration of variable renewable energy sources-a review. *Renew Energy* 2020; 145:2271–85.
- [28] Rahman A, Farrok O, Haque MM. Environmental impact of renewable energy source based electrical power plants: solar, wind, hydroelectric, biomass, geothermal, tidal, ocean, and osmotic. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2022;161: 12279.
- [29] Matsumoto KI, Matsumura Y. Challenges and economic effects of introducing renewable energy in a remote island: a case study of Tsushima Island, Japan. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2022;162:112456.
- [30] Islam S, Iqbal A, Marzband M, Khan I, Al-Wahedi AM. State-of-the-art vehicle-to-everything mode of operation of electric vehicles and its future perspectives. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2022;166:112574.
- [31] Yang Y, Bremner S, Menictas C, Kay M. Modelling and optimal energy management for battery energy storage systems in renewable energy systems: a review. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2022;167:112671.
- [32] Ansarin M, Ghiassi-Farrokhfal Y, Ketter W, Collins J. A review of equity in electricity tariffs in the renewable energy era. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2022; 161:112333.
- [33] Bekirsky N, Hoicka CE, Brisbois MC, Camargo LR. Many actors amongst multiple renewables: a systematic review of actor involvement in complementarity of renewable energy sources. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2022;161:112368.
- [34] Fearnside PM. Environmental and social impacts of hydroelectric dams in Brazilian Amazonia: implications for the aluminum industry. *World Dev* 2016;77: 48–65.
- [35] *Electricity from renewable resources: status, prospects, and impediments*. Washington, D.C: THE NATIONAL ACADEMIES PRESS; 2010.
- [36] Xu X, Tan Y, Yang G. Environmental impact assessments of the three Gorges project in China: issues and interventions. *Earth Sci Rev* 2013;124:115–25.
- [37] Nazir MS, Mahdi AJ, Bilal M, Sohail HM, Ali N, Iqbal HM. Environmental impact and pollution-related challenges of renewable wind energy paradigm - a review. *Sci Total Environ* 2019;683:436–44.
- [38] Nazir MS, Ali N, Bilal M, Iqbal HM. Potential environmental impacts of wind energy development: a global perspective. *Curr Opin Environ Sci health* 2020;13: 85–90.
- [39] May R, Nygard T, Falkdalen U, Astrom J, Hamre O, Stokke BG. Paint it black: efficacy of increased wind turbine rotor blade visibility to reduce avian fatalities. *Ecol Evol* 2020;10:8927–35.
- [40] Healy ML, Dahlben LJ, Isaacs JA. Environmental assessment of single walled carbon nanotube processes. *J Ind Ecol* 2008;12(3):376–93.
- [41] Balali MH, Nouri N, Omrani E, Nasiri A, Otieno W. An overview of the environmental, economic, and material developments of the solar and wind sources coupled with the energy storage systems. *Int J Energy Res* 2017;41: 1948–62. May.
- [42] *Environmental impacts of solar power*. Union of Concerned Scientists; 2003. <https://www.ucsusa.org/resources/environmental-impacts-solarpower#referencs>. [Accessed 1 February 2020].
- [43] Tsoutsos T, Frantzeskaki N, Gekas V. Environmental impacts from the solar energy technologies. *Energy Pol* 2005;33:289–96.
- [44] Breeze P. Solar integration and the environmental impact of solar power. In: *Solar power generation*. Academic Press; 2016. p. 81–7.
- [45] Mwasilu F, Justo JJ, Kim EK, Do TD, Jung JW. Electric vehicles and smart grid interaction: a review on vehicle to grid and renewable energy sources integration. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2014;34:501–16.
- [46] Battke B, Schmidt TS, Grosspietsch D, Hoffmann VH. A review and probabilistic model of lifecycle costs of stationary batteries in multiple applications. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2013;25:240–50.
- [47] Hussain A, Bui VH, Baek JW, Kim HM. Stationary energy storage system for fast EV charging stations: simultaneous sizing of battery and converter. *Energies* 2019;12:4516.
- [48] Ding H, Hu Z, Song Y. Value of the energy storage system in an electric bus fast charging station. *Appl Energy* 2015;157:630–9.
- [49] Bao Y, Luo Y, Zhang W, Huang M, Wang LY, Jiang JA. Bi-level optimization approach to charging load regulation of electric vehicle fast charging stations based on a battery energy storage system. *Energies* 2018;11:229.
- [50] Sbordone D, Bertini I, Di Pietra B, Falvo M, Genovese A, Martirano L. EV fast charging stations and energy storage technologies: a realimplementation in the smart micro grid paradigm. *Elec Power Syst Res* 2015;120:96–108.
- [51] Sun Y, Zhao Z, Yang M, Jia D, Pei W, Xu B. Overview of energy storage in renewable energy power fluctuation mitigation. *CSEE Journal of Power and Energy Systems* 2019;6(1):160–73.
- [52] Barman P, Dutta L, Azzopardi B. Electric vehicle battery supply chain and critical materials: a brief survey of state of the art. *Energies* 2023;16(8):3369.
- [53] *Unlocking Growth in Battery Cell Manufacturing for Electric Vehicles*, <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/operations/ourinsights/unlocking-growth-in-battery-cell-manufacturing-for-electricvehicles>, [Accessed 2 August 2022].
- [54] Sharma P, Bhatti TS. A Review on electrochemical double-layer capacitors. *Energy Covers Manag* 2010;5:2901–12.
- [55] Kramer AE. Billionaire backs a gas-electric hybrid car to be built in Russia. 2014. . [Accessed 2 October 2016].
- [56] Jiang Z, Dougal RA. A compact digitally controlled fuel cell/battery hybrid power source. *IEEE Trans Ind Electron* 2006;53:1094–104.
- [57] Thounchong P, Rael S, Davat B. Control strategy of fuel cell/supercapacitors hybrid power sources for electric vehicle. *J Power Sources* 2006;158:806–14.
- [58] Hansen JG. An assessment of flywheel high power energy storage technology for hybrid vehicles. The Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) report; 2012.
- [59] Bradley TH, Frank AA. Design, demonstration and sustainability impact assessments for plug-in hybrid electric vehicles. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2009;13:115–28.
- [60] Ayad MY, Becherif M, Henni A. Vehicle hybridizations with fuel cell, supercapacitors and batteries by sliding mode control. *Renew Energy* 2011;36: 2627–34.
- [61] Solero L, Lidozzi A, Pomilio JA. Design of multiple-input power converter for hybrid vehicles. *IEEE Trans Power Electron* 2005;20:1007–16.
- [62] Tu H, Feng H, Srdic S, Lukic S. Extreme fast charging of electric vehicles: a technology overview. *IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification* 2019;5(4):861–78.
- [63] Khan S, Ahmad A, Ahmad F, Shafaati Shemami M, Saad Alam M, Khateeb S. A comprehensive review on solar powered electric vehicle charging system. *Smart Science* 2018;6(1):54–79.
- [64] Tank I, Vignesh S, Bhatshvar YK, Vora KC. Vehicle to grid (V2G): booster for EV adaptation in India. In: 2021 IEEE 2nd international conference on smart technologies for power, energy and control (STPEC). IEEE; 2021. p. 1–6.
- [65] Thompson AW, Perez Y. Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) energy services, value streams, and regulatory policy implications. *Energy Pol* 2020;137:111136.
- [66] E-AMRIT, <https://e-amrit.niti.gov.in/energy/>; [Accessed 1 June 2023].
- [67] Raboaca MS, Meheden M, Musat A, Viziteu A, Creanga A, Vlad V, Lavric A. An overview and performance evaluation of open charge point protocol from an electromobility concept perspective. *Int J Energy Res* 2022;46(2):523–43.
- [68] Mouli GRC, Kaptein J, Bauer P, Zeman M. Implementation of dynamic charging and V2G using Chademo and CCS/Combo DC charging standard. In: *IEEE transportation electrification conference and Expo (ITEC)*; 2016. p. 1–6.
- [69] Garofalaki Z, Kosmanos D, Moschoyiannis S, Kallergis D, Douligieris C. Electric vehicle charging: a survey on the security issues and challenges of the open charge point protocol (OCPP). *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*; 2022.
- [70] *Open charge alliance*. <https://www.openchargealliance.org/>. [Accessed 28 September 2022].
- [71] *Open charge alliance-Our mission*. <https://www.openchargealliance.org/about-us/>; 2022. [Accessed 28 September 2022].
- [72] Mouftah HT, Erol-Kantarci M. *Smart grid: networking, Data Management, and business models*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: CRC Press; 2017.
- [73] *European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, C. L/evy-Bencheon, and E.Darra (Eur. Union Agency Netw. Inf. Security, Athens, Greece)*. In: *CyberSecurity for smart cities—an architecture model for public transport*; 2016. <https://doi.org/10.2824/846575>.
- [74] Mai TT, Jadun P, Logan JS, McMillan CA, Muratori M, Steinberg D C, Nelson B. *Electrification futures study: scenarios of electric technology adoption and power consumption for the United States (No. NREL/TP-6A20-71500)*. Golden, CO (United States): National Renewable Energy Lab.(NREL); 2018.
- [75] Hutchinson N, Bird L. Using renewables for electric vehicle demand: a review of utility program designs and implementation strategies. 2019.
- [76] Knapp L, O'Shaughnessy E, Heeter J, Mills S, DeCicco JM. Will consumers really pay for green electricity? Comparing stated and revealed preferences for residential programs in the United States. *Energy Res Social Sci* 2020;65:101457.
- [77] Arpan LM, Xu X, Raney AA, Chen CF, Wang Z. Politics, values, and morals: assessing consumer responses to the framing of residential renewable energy in the United States. *Energy Res Social Sci* 2018;46:321–31.

- [78] O'Shaughnessy E, Heeter J, Gattaciecchia J, Sauer J, Trumbull K, Chen E. Empowered communities: the rise of community choice aggregation in the United States. *Energy Pol* 2019;132:1110–9.
- [79] MacDonald S, Eyre N. An international review of markets for voluntary green electricity tariffs. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2018;91:180–92.
- [80] Zhang L, Jiang D, Imran M. Feasibility analysis of China's carbon taxation policy responding to the carbon tariff scheme of USA. *Carbon Letters* 2019;29(1): 99–107.
- [81] Schleich J, Schuler J, Pfaff M, Frank R. Renewable rebound: empirical evidence from household electricity tariff switching (No. S07/2021). Working Paper Sustainability and Innovation; 2021.
- [82] Orenstein J, Fladmark M. Community energy trading in Texas: potential revenue streams for helping make community solar sustainable. In: Proceedings of the American solar energy society. Cham: National Conference Springer; 2022. p. 3–9.
- [83] Michaud G. Perspectives on community solar policy adoption across the United States. *Renewable Energy Focus* 2020;33:1–15.
- [84] McDougall, L., A. Donnelly, and K. Chandra. "EV360 Whitepaper: Austin Energy's residential" off peak" electric vehicle charging subscription pilot approach, findings and utility toolkit" Austin Energy, nd Accessed: 27/May/2022.
- [85] Zhang S, Tang Y. Optimal schedule of grid-connected residential PV generation systems with battery storages under time-of-use and step tariffs. *J Energy Storage* 2019;23:175–82.
- [86] Li K, Liu L, Wang F, Wang T. Dui/c N, Shafie-khah M, & Catalao J P. Impact factors analysis on the probability characterized effects of time of use demand response tariffs using association rule mining method. *Energy Convers Manag* 2019;197:111891.
- [87] Ferro G, Paolucci M, Robba M. Optimal charging and routing of electric vehicles with power constraints and time-of-use energy prices. *IEEE Trans Veh Technol* 2020;69(12):14436–47.
- [88] Setting a new standard. <https://greatriverenergy.com/renewables/>. [Accessed 12 October 2022].
- [89] Austin Energy. <https://austinenergy.com/ae/>. [Accessed 13 October 2022].
- [90] EV-go. <https://www.evgo.com/charging-solutions/government-andutilities/>. [Accessed 13 October 2022].
- [91] Gre. <https://greatriverenergy.com/>. [Accessed 13 October 2022].
- [92] Smud. <https://www.smud.org/>. [Accessed 13 October 2022].
- [93] Xcel energy. <https://my.xcelenergy.com/s/stateselector?return=%2Fs%2F>. [Accessed 13 October 2022].
- [94] Pepco. <https://www.pepco.com/Pages/default.aspx#>. [Accessed 13 October 2022].
- [95] Sce. <https://www.sce.com/>. [Accessed 13 October 2022].
- [96] Hawaiian. <https://www.hawaiianelectric.com/>. [Accessed 13 October 2022].
- [97] Tva. <https://www.tva.com/>. [Accessed 13 October 2022].
- [98] Wang S, Tarroja B, Schell LS, Shaffer B, Samuelsen S. Prioritizing among the end uses of excess renewable energy for cost-effective greenhouse gas emission reductions. *Appl Energy* 2019;235:284–98.
- [99] Schiebahn S, Grube T, Robinus M, Tietze V, Kumar B, Stolten D. Power to gas: technological overview, systems analysis and economic assessment for a cast study in Germany. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2015;40(12):4285–94.
- [100] Gallo AB, Simoes-Moreira JR, Costa HKM, Santos MM, Santos EMd. Energy storage in the energy transition context: a technology review. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2016;65:800–22.
- [101] Prajapati MSG, Vyas SR. Energy management strategies of grid connected renewable source for EV charging station. 2021.
- [102] Goke L, Kendziorski M, Kemfert C, von Hirschhausen C. Accounting for spatiality of renewables and storage in transmission planning. *Energy Econ* 2022;113: 106190.
- [103] Tian X, Zhou Y, Morris B, You F. Sustainable design of Cornell University campus energy systems toward climate neutrality and 100% renewables. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2022;161:112383.
- [104] Anwar MB, Muratori M, Jadun P, Hale E, Bush B, Denholm P, Podkaminer K. Assessing the value of electric vehicle managed charging: a review of methodologies and results. *Energy Environ Sci* 2022;15:466–98.
- [105] Pratt RM, Bernal LE. Distribution system V1G PEV charging impacts report (No. PNNL-27206). Richland, WA (United States): Pacific Northwest National Lab. (PNNL); 2018.
- [106] Sovacool 1180 BK, Kester J, Noel L, de Rubens GZ. Actors, business models, and innovation activity systems for vehicle-to-grid (V2G) technology: a comprehensive review. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2020;131:109963.
- [107] Shariff SM, Iqbal D, Alam MS, Ahmad F. A state of the art review of electric vehicle to grid (V2G) Technology. *IOP Conf Ser Mater Sci Eng* 2019;561(1): 012103.
- [108] Habib HUR, Subramaniam U, Waqar A, Farhan BS, Kotb KM, Wang S. Energy cost optimization of hybrid renewables based V2G microgrid considering multi objective function by using artificial bee colony optimization. *IEEE Access* 2020; 8:62076–93.